

D7.1

The HEIR website and visual identity

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Executive summary

This deliverable outlines the website development for the HEIR project (www.heir202.eu) and the visual identity of the project. In brief, the document depicts website's infrastructure and content. It outlines the initial content and structure of the site at launch which will serve as a collaboration tool for knowledge, experience, and best practice sharing, as well as consolidating results and supporting dissemination. This deliverable will be closely linked to D7.3 Dissemination strategy and activities, stakeholders' engagement, and business opportunities-P1 and D7.4 Dissemination strategy and activities, stakeholders' engagement, and business opportunities-P2.

The HEIR website aims to act as a powerful tool for boosting information flow between all entities involved, while additional social channels (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube) will intensify the key messages from the project website. It will act as the focal point for web-based dissemination and communication activity by mainly providing information about the HEIR project for numerous target audiences, both technical and non-technical, inside and outside the health sector. The public website presents the project brand and provides well-presented non-confidential information, such as project concept, partners, core objectives and workplan, project news and contact information. Links to all social media profiles are also provided. The rationale behind layout decisions, content structure of the HEIR website was to establish a visually attractive, easy to navigate, informative website. Sections for publications and deliverables, media and downloads have been included in the website structure to support relevant content as it becomes available during the project timeline.

The visual identity and in particular the logo is aimed to be used on any material to allow for easy recognition of the project. The visual identity and online presence comply with all communication requirements set forth by the European Commission. The funding source and Grant Agreement number are mentioned on the website as well as on all communication material.

Section 2 presents the visual identity of the project.

Section 3 presents the social media channels created as part of the communications and dissemination strategy to increase general awareness of the HEIR results.

Section 4 presents an outline of the website infrastructure and technical components. More specifically, the website structure is presented and features with respect to the underlying platform are described.

Section 5 of this document outlines the content of the public pages of the site including screenshots from each page.

Section 6 outlines the website's statistics as they are derived via google analytics platform.

Finally, section 7 concludes the present document with a brief outline of future action and updates regarding the HEIR website

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List of Abbreviations

URL Uniform Resource Locator

WP Work package

M Month

D Deliverable

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document identity

The purpose of Deliverable 7.1 of HEIR is to briefly outline the visual identity and the initial setup of the project's website. It describes the initial content and structure of the site at launch and presents the social media channels which will serve as collaboration tools for knowledge, experience and best practice sharing as well as consolidating results and supporting dissemination.

1.2 Intended readership

D7.1 is a public document (PU) and therefore is intended for the European Commission, the HEIR Project Officer, the members of the HEIR consortium, members of other H2020-funded projects as well as the general public.

The intended readership included a broad range of different target audiences both technical and non-technical including health care networks, IT security associations, eHealth service providers, technology providers, academic and research institutions, other related national and EU-funded projects, Commission Staff, media, and the wider public.

1.3 Relationship with other HEIR Deliverables

This deliverable will be closely linked to D7.3, “Dissemination strategy and activities, stakeholders’ engagement and business opportunities-P1”, due in Month 18 of the project and D7.4, “Dissemination strategy and activities, stakeholders’ engagement and business opportunities-P2”, due in Month 36 of the project.

2. Visual identity

Logos are the key graphic identity elements and essential to build a successful dissemination campaign for any project. The HEIR logo design has been carried out in a way that can be a representative of the project's concept and vision.

The HEIR logo can be seen below:

Figure 1: HEIR logo

Microsoft PowerPoint has been utilized for the logo creation. The logo comprises project's acronym HEIR and three icons. Bahnschrift SemiBold Condensed font and Font Color coded #17375E in RGB color space were used to create the text. Three icons are connected with a line to the three of the four corners of the text. These icons, each of which is located inside a circle, are related to medical symbols (cross), cybersecurity symbols (lock) and a combination of medical and technology symbols (a person icon and a cross symbol on a laptop screen).

All communication and dissemination activities will be carried out using this logo which will be used for all materials, including PowerPoint presentations, technical reports, newsletters and other promotional material. The project logo is available for the entire consortium and can be downloaded from the SVN repository of the project, an internal online collaborative platform, where all partners can securely share documents.

3. Social Media

Several HEIR activities (e.g., publicity material, e-meetings) will be carried out to maximise project's social media presence, and engage a large number of audiences:

- The selection of channels forming the HEIR social media grid are the most appropriate for targeting specific audiences: Those are: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube.
- A content maintenance plan will be put in place for managing and streamlining content across multiple channels.
- HEIR logo and consistent channel names will be used in all promotional material to increase brand awareness and maximise visibility.
- Messages will be kept simple, while visual media will be used abundantly to the context of each channel.
- HEIR website contains a link to Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook accounts.

The above actions will assist in being able to accurately and continuously measure the presence and performance of HEIR on social media.

3.1 Roles – Responsibility

- A Gmail global account (username: heir2020eu) serves as the content admin for all HEIR social media accounts. By this account, administration and maintenance services occur having as target to drive traffic through different accounts.
- STS will act proactively to ensure the latest HEIR related information as well as relevant (to HEIR objectives) announcements will be posted on the social media accounts; STS also is responsible for the content and technical maintenance of social media accounts.
- All visual elements are to be approved by the PC.
- HEIR partners will be encouraged to share project social media channels on their websites and all the communication related to the project.

3.2 Facebook

The HEIR Facebook page (**Heir-H2020**, Figure 2) can be found at: <https://www.facebook.com/Heir-H2020-100315005196755>

Facebook page - still in the start-up stage - will be used for public project communication in the form of pictures and videos to attract citizens and crowds' interest.

Figure 2: HEIR Facebook profile

3.3 Twitter

The HEIR Twitter page (@h2020_heir, Figure 3) can be found at: https://twitter.com/h2020_heir

The Twitter page will be used to communicate with stakeholders through networking. Tweets can include project news, announcements and status updates, as well as relevant information from other EU projects, stakeholder retweets and responses to other users' tweets.

Figure 3: HEIR Twitter profile

3.4 LinkedIn

The HEIR LinkedIn page (**HEIR H2020 Project**, Figure 4) can be found at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/heir-h2020-project>

The LinkedIn page targets the professional community, and as such will promote information to the partners of the project and people strongly interested in HEIR activities. It will be useful also for building networks with specific HEIR target groups, including SMEs, Regulatory Bodies, Researchers, Policy makers, and individuals and entities involved in any of the fields relevant to HEIR.

Figure 4: HEIR LinkedIn profile

3.5 YouTube

The HEIR Twitter page (HEIR H2020, Figure 4) can be found at: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC_boW9_lfvcZxNpbSIQ8acw/

The YouTube page will be used to communication with both stakeholders and general public through videos from outreach activities, events, demonstrations etc.

Figure 5: HEIR YouTube channel

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4. Website

4.1 Overview

The HEIR website has been designed and developed by ITML. The developing activities started in M1 and the website launch took place at the beginning of M2 (October 2020) it was ready for full operation.

The design of the site was based on the ease of access and navigation to it by the end user. In addition, the presentation of the website's content (including project's objectives, consortium, use cases, workplan etc.) follows a user-friendly approach. With respect to its look and design, the HEIR website takes full advantage of the project's logo colour pallet.

4.2 URL

The following URL has been acquired by the HEIR consortium and is intended to be used by Internet users for accessing the project website which is publicly available from October 1st, 2020.

<https://heir2020.eu>

4.3 Technical Details

Table 1 below outlines Technical Details with reference to HEIR website.

HEIR Website Technical Details	
Domain	https://heir2020.eu
Servers	Web Server Apache / 2.4.25 (Debian)
Content Management System (CMS)	Drupal Version 8.9.7
PHP Version	7.1.20
MySQL Version	5.7.32

Table 1: HEIR website Technical Details

4.4 Website structure

The HEIR website has a simple structure as it is illustrated in Figure 6. The project's website consists of a public domain where the visitors are able to gather information with respect to the project, download the project's publicly available dissemination material (like accepted deliverables, brochures and other informative documents or publications) and find information about the HEIR consortium.

Figure 6. HEIR Website Structure

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5. Website Content

The HEIR website consists of four (4) main pages:

- **Project:** providing a concise description of the project vision and innovations, the work plan is going to be followed, the architecture of HEIR's platform and the four use cases.
- **Consortium:** detailing the partners and their role in the project.
- **Results:** where users can download HEIR-related publications, public deliverables or project dissemination material and
- **News & Events:** where project and pilot news are regularly posted.

The following subsections outline all the pages mentioned above including a screenshot for each page.

5.1 Homepage

The homepage consists of separate sections with basic project information. These sections are namely Objectives, Work Packages, HEIR Use Cases, Partners, and News & Events. There is also a section with four links to At a Glance, Vision, Innovation and Architecture sections. The footer section of HEIR homepage consists of a distinct area with links to the HEIR social media accounts, a list with the key facts of the project and acknowledgement of funding from the EU under the Horizon 2020 programme. A snapshot of the HEIR website homepage is presented in Figure 7 below.

Figure 7 – HEIR Website Homepage

5.2 Project

The Project submenu, Figure 8, comprises six pages namely Architecture, At a Glance, Innovations, Work Plan, Vision and Use Cases, that give website visitors a chance to explore all aspects of the project.

Figure 8 – PROJECT submenu

5.2.1 Architecture

A high-level architecture structure of the envisioned HEIR platform.

Figure 9 - HEIR architecture

5.2.2 At a Glance

An abstract about the usefulness of the project in today's very demanding health ecosystems.

Figure 10 - HEIR At a Glance

5.2.3 Innovations

A list of innovations brought by HEIR project.

Figure 11 - HEIR Innovations

5.2.4 Work Plan

A detailed description of the objectives and the outcomes of all nine Work packages and a depiction of how they interact with each other.

Figure 12 - HEIR Work Plan

5.2.5 Vision

A brief description of project's vision.

Figure 13 - HEIR Vision

5.2.6 Use Cases

Use cases page comprises four informative description for all four diverse health pilots.

Figure 14 - HEIR Use Cases

5.3 Consortium

The consortium page, Figure 15, outlines each member of the HEIR consortium with a short description, their role in the project, corresponding logo and link to the official website for each consortium member.

The screenshot displays the HEIR Consortium website with a navigation menu (PROJECT, CONSORTIUM, RESULTS, NEWS & EVENTS) and a map of Europe. Below the map, three partner profiles are shown:

Institut Mines-Télécom
 Institut Mines-Télécom is a major science and technology institute and a public institution dedicated to higher education and research. Always attentive to the economic world, IMT combines strong academic and scientific legitimacy with a concrete presence alongside companies. It offers training in engineering and management up to PhD level, and focuses on the major transformations of the 21st century: digital technologies, the environment and energy, industry and education. The IMT schools are ranked among the leading graduate schools in France.

The department involved in the project is the cybersecurity group at Télécom SudParis, one of the schools affiliated with IMT. The group is active in many aspects of cybersecurity, including privacy and protection of personal data, cybersecurity for critical infrastructures, networks and protocols security, and attack detection and mitigation. The group has participated in many collaborative projects at the French and EU level and coordinated several EU projects.

ROLE IN THE PROJECT

IMT will act as the coordinator of the HEIR project. As such, it will provide support to the HEIR partners for their activities inside the project. On the research standpoint, IMT has been investigating network security and the Internet of Things, developing expertise in anomaly detection for these environments. It also has activities related to training through a labelled cybersecurity curriculum, that will leverage the results of HEIR to provide training to engineers and personnel in the healthcare sector. We have opened in 2019 a specific track for digital training in the healthcare sector, where the training program focuses on the needs of hospitals and care centers to develop the appropriate digital training program for both master students and professionals.

FORTH
 INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE

FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS (FORTH)
 The Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH), established in 1983, is the largest Greek State R&D Centre. FORTH hosts six major Research Institutes. The Institute of Computer Science (ICS) has established an internationally acknowledged excellence in conducting basic and applied research, developing applications and products, and providing services.

ROLE IN THE PROJECT

FORTH will bring in the project innovative solutions regarding the threat classification, anomaly detection, vulnerability analysis and monitoring. It will support on adapting security components suitable to HEIR ecosystem. In addition, FORTH will take the stakeholders' engagement and ecosystem building between CERTs and healthcare providers. Finally, FORTH will contribute and support on the legal and regulatory aspect of the HEIR platform.

AEGIS

AEGIS IT RESEARCH LTD (AEGIS)
 AEGIS IT RESEARCH UG is a research and development company based in Germany developing and managing innovative IT solutions for numerous business sectors. It is based on a highly effective professional team consisting of talented researchers and top-class IT experts from all over the world. This

Figure 15 - HEIR Consortium

5.4 Results

The Results section consists of three separate sub-pages namely Deliverables (Figure 16), Publications (Figure 17) and Dissemination materials (Figure 18). Website visitors can download corresponding content from each sub-page.

Deliverable No.	Deliverable name	Type	Dissemination level
D1.1	HEIR innovations for healthcare systems	Report	Public
D1.2	Positioning of HEIR	Report	Confidential
D1.3	System Architecture definition	Report	Public
D2.1	The HEIR facilitators package: MVP	Demonstrator	Public
D2.2	The HEIR facilitators package: 1st complete version	Demonstrator	Public
D2.3	The HEIR facilitators package: Final complete version	Demonstrator	Public

Figure 16 - HEIR Deliverables

Figure 17 - HEIR Publications

Figure 18 - HEIR Dissemination Materials

5.5 News & Events

The News & Events page, figure 19, will provide regular updates about HEIR project containing all the news and events in which project partners attend and present the project.

Figure 19 - HEIR News & Events I

From there, by selecting a specific topic, visitors are transferred to a new page which contains more information about the specific topic as well as a section with tweets from HEIR’s official tweeter account. (Figure 20)

Figure 20 - HEIR News & Events II

5.6 Contact Details and Social Media

On the footer section of the website detailed contact information and links to social media accounts of the project are displayed, as shown in figure 21.

Figure 21 - HEIR Website Footer

5.7 Personal Data Protection & Cookies Policy

Once visitors access HEIR website, a banner appears at the bottom of the page providing them with basic information about the use of cookies that takes place on the website. In this banner there is a link redirecting them to website's personal data protection and Cookies Policy, where there is a full description of the policies.

Finally, at the footer of the page, there is also a distinctive hyperlink to these policies, and thus, visitors can access them regardless the page they are at that time.

6. Website Statistics

The HEIR consortium will utilize the Google Analytics platform for project’s website activity monitoring and analysis in order to measure progress and impact. Google Analytics is an effective tool in terms of tracking web site traffic and get significant quantity of useful data with respect to dissemination impact in the sense of raise of public awareness.

Considering that the HEIR website has been registered to Google Analytics Platform since October 5th 2020, as shown in figure 22, it stands to reason that no conclusions or even observations can be derived at this point.

Figure 22 - HEIR website Google Analytics Report

7. Conclusions & Future Plans

The HEIR website aims to act as a powerful tool for boosting information flow between all entities involved. It will also be used to disseminate targeted information to relevant interested parties. Considering the fact that the project website has been publicly accessible since the early stage of the project, it is anticipated that several updates will be implemented as a result of adaptation to constantly effective online dissemination activity and emerging project results. To this end, revisions regarding the usability of the website with respect to the end-user will be made in addition to updates with contribution of content by all consortium members. HEIR project website will be enriched with more information including audio-visual content as the project progresses.

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